

NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL IVD eCRF CONSENSUS

SECTION 1: DEMOGRAPHICS

- Subject fiscal code
- Visit date
- Birth date
- Age
- Sex
- Years of education

SECTION 2: BEHAVIORAL AND FUNCTIONAL ASSESSMENT	<i>Raw score</i>	<i>Max</i>
• IADL [1]		8
• ADL (Katz 1963) [2]		6
• Neuropsychiatric Inventory (NPI) [3]		
○ Delusions		12
○ Hallucinations		12
○ Agitation		12
○ Depression/dysphoria		12
○ Anxiety		12
○ Euphoria/elation		12
○ Apathy/indifference		12
○ Disinhibition		12
○ Irritability/lability		12
○ Aberrant motor behavior		12
○ Sleep and nighttime behavior disorders		12
○ Appetite and eating disorders		12
○ Total score		144

SECTION 3: NEUROPSYCHOLOGICAL ASSESSMENT	<i>Raw score</i>	<i>Max.</i>
• Mini Mental State Examination (MMSE) [4]		30
• Digit span forward [5]		
• Digit span backward [5]		
• Spatial span forward [5]		
• Spatial span backward [5]		
• 15 words of Rey, immediate recall [6]		75
• 15 words of Rey, delayed recall [6]		15
• Copy of the complex figure of Rey-Osterrieth [7]		36
• Delayed recall of the complex figure of Rey-Osterrieth [7]		36
• BADA naming test [8]		30
• Trail Making Test (TMT) [9]		
○ TMT A (sec)		
○ TMT B (sec)		
○ TMT B-A (sec)		
• Stroop test [10]		
○ Time [sec]		
○ Errors		
• Phonemic fluency (letters F, A, and S) [6]		
• Semantic fluency (fruits, animals, and car brands) [11]		

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